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RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

Title: SOP for replacing glass liner and septum of GC Q – Exactive

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Author: Kateřina Coufalíková

IMPORTANT

- Before each batch/measurement it is necessary to replace the Glass Liner and Septum to prevent contamination
- To prevent needle destroy: After you used liner (for SPME) put back the (splitless/splitt) liner to GC
- When turning Off the GC: first turn off the temperature and then turn off the carrier gas flow
- When turning ON the GC: first turn on the carrier gas flow

NOTE: Turning ON/OFF GC in reverse order may cause column destroy

Preparing GC for maintenance

- 1) Turn off the temperature(Go to Touch Screen Main Menu > Maintenance > Front (SSL) > Cool this zone > Yes > Begin Cooldown)

NOTE: Wait until is the temperature at least ~ 60°C

- 2) Turn the carrier gas flow of front inlet Off (Instrument Control > Front Inlet (SSL) > Column flow > Off)

To replace Glass Liner

- 3) Open the flap module
- 4) Unscrew the right nut
- 5) Remove the septum holder and using tweezers remove the old liner with liner seal (ring)
- 6) Take new liner (hold only the upper part of the liner) and put liner seal (ring) to liner
- 7) Gently insert new liner with liner seal (ring) to the injector and push it gently towards the button of the injector. Hold by hand only the upper part of the liner. (Be careful not to break the glass liner).
- 8) Close the septum holder. Screw and gently tighten the right nut

Figure 1. Liner with liner seal (ring)

Figure 2. Split Splitless Injector Components

To replace the septum

- 1) Unscrew and open the septum cap
- 2) With tweezers remove the old septum
- 3) Place new septum and push it with fingers
- 4) Screw and gently tighten the septum cap
- 5) Turn the carrier gas on (Instrument Control > Front Inlet (SSL) > Column flow 1.2 mL/min)

Check if the gas flow gradually increases and then is constant > in system is no leak

- 6) Turn on the temperature (Maintenance > Front (SSL) > Col this zone > No > Restore temperatures)

7) Wait minimum 30 minutes for stabilization system